
THE IMPACT OF MOTIVATION ON EMPLOYEE'S PRODUCTIVITY (A CASE STUDY OF OLAM NIGERIA LIMITED MAKURDI, BENUE STATE, NIGERIA)

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ABSTRACT- *This project focuses attention on the Impact of Motivation on Employee Productivity – A Case Study of Olam Nigeria Limited. As the title of the project implies, attempts were made to bring out those motivational factors that influence and energize workers to behave the way they do. The study has become imperative given the company's drive to increase productivity and profit. The instruments used for data collection were questionnaires and personal interviews. The researcher reviewed various works on the subject matter. The difference peculiarities and drawbacks of these theories were brought out. The major findings of the study are: some employees may be happy, but remain unproductive, a motivation does not guarantee high level of performance, and an increased salary or improving work conditions does not create a state of employee satisfaction. Appropriate guidelines and suggestions were offered to improve staff motivation in the Company.*

Keywords: Motivation; Employee; Productivity; Questionnaires; Personal Interviews; Olam Nigeria Ltd.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The study and management of human efforts is one of the traditional areas of business and is best understood through motivation theories. Essentially, it deals with the complex system of men in organization and their utilization. Consequently, efficient operation can be traced to efficient and well-motivated employees.

If one is to be effective in the management of human *resources*, it is necessary to have an understanding of the psychological functioning of the individual. Just as the employee has certain wants, the organization also expects certain types of behaviours from its employees. The managerial responsibility for deciding this behaviour is usually termed **directing** or **motivation**. In essence, it is a skill in aligning employee and organizational interests so that behaviour results in the achievement of employee's wants simultaneously with the attainment of organizational objectives.

The term **motivation** originally was derived from the Latin word **Movere** this means, **to move**. An analysis of major definitions indicates that motivation is primarily concerned with:

- What energizes human behaviour
- What directs or channels such behaviour
- How this behaviour is maintained or sustained

The study of motivation therefore is a study of variables that initiate, energise and frequently guide behaviour. Theories of motivation attempt to conceptual framework for the understanding of the existence of various motive states.

Motive constitute in intervening variables between the stimulus and response. Motive can be classified as learned and unlearned, higher learned and secondary drive and physiology or primary drive. Drive may be defined as physiology or stimulus that arises towards a goal. Drive can be categorized as being positively or negatively directed. Physiological drive includes hunger, thirst, temperature, regulation and sleep. It is essential to the survival of the body that balance is maintained among internal organs. The general term given to these physiological conditions is Haemostatic

Psychologists generally agree that all behaviour is motivated and that people have reasons for doing things they do or for behaving in a particular manner. The various forms of behaviour and attitudinal disposition manner which organisations require of their employees in order to achieve set of goals depend on the kind of reward existing in the organisation. And these rewards vary from one organisation to another and they include the following; opportunity in the company for advancement, job security, salary/ wages, medical health facilities, luncheon voucher, pension scheme, credit for the job done – recognition, vocation and holiday practices, housing, transport, company attitudes towards employees, incentive scheme, and physical working conditions among others. These factors may have positive or negative influences on the performance of the staff and therefore, have a tendency of motivating staff to perform as required by management thus resulting in better performance, job satisfaction, increase output and efficiency in the organisation.

It is therefore necessary to know which categories of employee's value what item of reward more highly than they do other items, while some employees especially the senior once place more value on opportunity in the company for advancement, others particularly the junior employees may prefer more wages and salaries or job securities than other things.

This is because junior employees have not satisfied what Maslow in his hierarchy of needs theory described as physiological needs. These include the basic necessities of life as food, shelter and clothing. These employees particularly the junior ones require more money to satisfy these basic needs, hence their preference for more wages/ salary. The impact of motivation and incentive may therefore vary from category of employees to another in the organization hierarchy.

Management as is generally known is the act of getting people to do the things one want to do; management involves motivating people and any discussion of human motivation inevitably leads to the question of reward and incentive. Rewards/ incentives may be financial and non-financial. In fact, rewards or incentives for four Main purposes;

- (i) To persuade people to come work.
- (ii) To encourage people to work harder when they are at work.
- (iii) To help people to identify themselves with the objectives of the organisation.
- (iv) To show management appreciation of the employees contribution to the survival of the organisation, Gilchrist (1971).

According to Parker and Klemier (1951), "Management has at long last discovered that this is greater productivity and hence greater profit when workers are satisfied with their jobs; improves the moral of the employees and you improve proud productivity.

Likert (1961) is of the view that a highly motivated cooperative orientation towards the organisation and its objectives is achieved by harvesting effectively all the major motivational factors.

Motivation in its true perspective goes beyond achieving high moral. Employees may be happy but unproductive. It is on the ground that, it is stated that to understand motivation, we must firstly understand the nature of human needs. In essence various studies have shown the correlation between rewards and motivation in an organisation. A well-packaged incentive system coupled with appropriate reward has a tendency of influencing employees in the organisation. In fact, with increase motivation through attractive incentives and reward system, workers will be more satisfied with their works and hence put in the utmost best into achieving organisational goals and effectiveness.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

Of all the factors of production that have been identified in the world, the most dynamic appears to be the labour, that is, human effort. Workers who provide labour have their likes and dislikes, hope and aspirations, hence the need for one important management action-motivation.

To get people to work effectively in these dynamic environments of organizations therefore, the leadership styles of managers will have to change, as defined by many management scholars, the functions of managers is to get things done or achieve results through people (Follet 1966-1933). It is however, believed that for managers to achieve these results, they should have pre-knowledge of the behaviour of their subordinates. The employees (subordinates) on the other hand, should possess skill and knowledge so as to perform their job quite effectively. It must be emphasized that employees need to be

persuaded and induced to expend more time and effort on their jobs so as to collectively and attain the corporate objectives. The unique ways of energizing and activating these subordinates to achieve the set target is collectively referred to as “motivation”.

To sum the opinion of most behavioural scientist, one will realize that for motivation to be effective, the manager have to know whose things to do to activate their subordinates to act in a desired manner, hence the need to know some of the theories of motivation

This research reviews the works of Maslow (1954-1970), Herzberg (1957), McClelland (1961), McGregor (1960), Vroom (1964), Likerts (1967) and Ouchi (1981).

2.2 THEORIES OF MOTIVATION

2.2.1 Abraham Maslow’s Hierarchy of Needs

Maslow’s theory of motivation stresses two fundamental premises – man is a wanting animal whose needs depend on what he already has. Only needs not yet fulfilled can influence behaviour – an adequately fulfilled needs does not motivate.

As soon as physiological needs are satisfied, the managers turn themselves to security needs.

1. **Love and belongingness (Social Need):** people want to be accepted by others for what they are. When social needs are not met, the mental health of the employee may be affected and may result in frequent absenteeism and low job satisfaction. Workers in an attempt to achieve these needs will value jobs that afford opportunities for social interaction among co-workers. Managers motivate workers towards these needs by acting in a particular supportive and permissive way that might be accepted by co-workers and taking part in extracurricular activities such as organized sports programmes.
2. **Self-Esteem/Ego Needs:** This includes the desire for self respect, achievement, adequacy, independence and freedom, recognition and reputation. Managers who focus on these needs tend to emphasize public reward and recognition for services; emphasis on skills required for success characterizes manager’s contact with employees.
3. **Self-Actualization:** The emergence of this need usually depend upon the prior satisfaction of previous needs disclosed above. Self-actualization needs refer to a man’s desire and fulfilment. Managers may motivate employees towards satisfying this need by involving the employees in decision-making, restructuring of jobs or special assignment that require their unique skills, to sum up, this is the need that pushes one to be creative, inventive and innovative because what a man can be, he must be.

2.2.2 Fredrick Herzberg’s Two-Factor Theory

The motivation-hygiene theory is credited to Herzberg. The “two-factor” theory as the name implies consist of:

- 1) Motivators, maintenance or satisfier factors
- 2) Hygiene or dissatisfies factors

The motivator factors offer lasting increase in job satisfaction and actually motivate the employee to higher performance. They are found in the job itself. They include:

- (i) Achievement
- (ii) Advancement/growth
- (iii) Recognition
- (iv) Responsibility
- (v) Work itself

The hygiene factors are essentially preventive as they minimize disaffection but on their own, they do not motivate.

- (i) Supervision
- (ii) Company policy
- (iii) Pay/salary
- (iv) Job security
- (v) Working condition

Management have always wondered why the provision of fringe benefits and other motivate policies have not resulted in increased productivity. The reason is that they are basically maintenance (hygiene) factors and not motivating factors.

2.2.3 David McClelland's Needs Theory

McClelland identified three types of basic motivating needs. He classified these needs into three:

- (i) Need for power
- (ii) Need for affiliation
- (iii) Need for achievement

Need for power

People with a high need for power have a great concern for exercising influence and control, desire position of leadership.

Need for achievement

People with high need for achievement have an intense desire for success and an equally intense fear for failure. They want feedback on how they are faring.

There is a necessity for a manager or entrepreneur to possess some degree of all three needs- that is, some needs for power and some needs for affiliation to go along with a strong need for achievement. But in the researcher's opinion, the dominant need is the one for achievement.

2.2.4 Douglas McGregor's Theories X and Y:

McGregor set forth two alternative views about the nature of people which he termed "theory X and theory Y" these theories are based on some assumptions.

Theory X Assumptions:

- (i) Human beings have an inherent dislike for work and will avoid work if they can
- (ii) Most people must be coerced or threatened with punished to get them to put adequate effort towards the achievement of an object.
- (iii) Human beings prefer to be directed, wish to avoid responsibilities and have relatively little ambition, yet above all they want security.

Theory Y Assumptions

- (i) Expenditure of physical and mental effort in work is as natural as play or rest
- (ii) It is assumed that commitment to objective is a function of the reward associated with their achievement.
- (iii) The average human being learns under proper conditions, not only to accept but to seek responsibility. The management style a manager in an organisation adopts can be determined by his assumption about human beings based on the theory by McGregor (1960).

2.2.5 Victor Vroom's Valence-Expectancy Theory:

Using his own terms, Vroom's theory may be stated as follows:

Motivational force = value X expectancy

Where: Motivational fore = the strength or a person's motivation

Valence = The strength of a person's preference for an outcome.

Expectancy = The probability that a particular action will lead to a desired outcome.

According to Vroom, an individual will be motivated to produce at high level if he perceives that his effort will result in a successful performance. In addition, the individual must perceive that a successful performance will result in outcome or rewards. The individual must specify how much he deserves the various rewards he will obtain, granted that he performs successfully. Desired outcomes can be of two types:-

- Intrinsic reward that relates directly to the nature of the work itself (for example, how interesting and challenging it is).
- Extrinsic rewards that do not relate directly to the nature of the work (for example salary increase and working conditions).

Basically, Vroom feels that motivation is a product of how much one wants something and one's estimate of the probability that a certain action or services off actions will lead to getting that thing.

2.2.6 Reusis Likert's Approach to Motivation

Likert (1967) claims that when an organisation is faced with the need to conserve cash, the most common reaction is to cut expenses and "tighten-up" operations. Likert studies shows that when cost cutting is applied insensitivity that is when management adopts a tough, take-it-or leave it attitude the reaction could be drastic.

Firstly, employees become resentful, hostile and distrustful towards management. Secondly, as a result of these attitudes, employees are likely to submit many more grievances than usual, work carelessly and wastefully restrict production and even leave the organisation to find employment elsewhere.

Likert postulated four systems of management. These are:

System I: Exploitative – Authoritative management. Here managers are highly autocrat and have little trust in subordinates.

System II: Benevolent – Authoritative management. These managers have a condescending confidence and trust in subordinates. They motivate with rewards and some fear and punishment.

System III: Consultative management. Here managers have substantial but no complete trust and confidence in subordinates.

System IV: Participative Management. These managers have complete trust and confidence in subordinates in all matters

2.3 THE MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS OF MOTIVATION THEORIES:

Abraham Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Theory

It is important to point out that man can never be fully satisfied. Therefore, the manager must not relent on his effort but continue to do his utmost best to find ways to satisfy his subordinates. To do this, the manager must seek ways of translating these concepts of human needs into supervisory practices, which will enable individuals to find greater fulfilment of all their needs. In fact, the manager must create a total work environment that will be conducive for self-motivation.

The hierarchy of needs theory will find a work place a very fertile ground for useful and fruitful application practice, that unmet needs of their employees may yet constitute the solution to the employees' motivational and low performance problems.

African managers might find out that in their usually autocratic, and despotic political environment that have dampened the moral of the citizenry, participate management and feedback programmes in their organisation will provide the avenue to satisfy the workers' esteem needs.

Also, in a political/economic environment that does not guarantee the average African employee the fulfilment of physiological and safety needs, a well articulate and honesty implemented housing programme will guarantee their employees the satisfaction of those basic needs and thereby increasing their job satisfaction and their morale and productivity.

Fredrick Hierarchy Two-Factor Theory

Organization need to include Herzberg motivators in the employee's tasks by creating the job content that will enable the employees to experience those motivators. In designing the work environment for the employee, the issue pertaining to the hygiene factors must be thoroughly examined and sued with case to avoid their negative consequences on the employee's performance.

In a study on the “motivational characteristics of financial rewards on Nigerian Workers”. Asika (1984) showed that for the Nigerian worker, financial rewards have three components;

- a) Reduction (or increase) in income
- b) Salaries and
- c) Fringe benefits

The study showed that in the employee’s perception, financial rewards generally have weak effect on the motivation to employees is selected to the level of employment. In other words, salary has strongest appeal to the junior employees and fringe benefits have strongest appeal to the senior management. It was further discovered that Nigerian employees are likely to increase productivity if financial rewards are tied to a measurable level of their work efforts or productivity.

David McClelland’s Needs Theory:

McClelland studies showed no relationship between achievement, motivation and genetic makeup of the individual, this is to say that achievement motivation can be learned by and developed in the individual. Thus, adults can be trained to acquire the motivation for achievement, so employers should therefore design training programmes incorporating the development of achievement motivation in their employees.

Since McClelland study has demonstrated that successful top-level executives are rich in high power motivation and that successful up-coming executives have high achievement motivation, recruiters of these two classes it should showed endeavour to look for these characteristics in prospective employees of their organisation.

It should also be noted that achievement motivated executives prefer challenging jobs of moderate difficulty. This implies that organizations should endeavours to challenge their executives with the type of tasks in order to sharpen the achievement motivation.

Douglas McGregor’s Theories X and Y:

The theory “X” assumption is pessimistic, static and rigid because control is imposed on the subordinates by the supervisor. In contrast theory “Y” is optimistic, dynamic and flexible with emphasis of self-direction and the integration of individual needs with organizational demand. Each set of assumptions will affect the way managers carryout their managerial functions and activities.

It seems obvious that the assumptions and approaches identified in theory X are wide spread in on-going organizations in Nigeria. Unless there are opportunities at work to satisfy the higher level needs, people will be deprived and their work behaviour will reflect this deprivation.

Vroom’s Valence – Expectancy Theory:

The valence-expectancy theory indicate that effort which is the strength of motivation depends on the value of rewards and the perceived energy a person believed is required and the likelihood of actually receiving the reward. The perceived effort and probability assess

their reward structures through careful planning, management by objective (MBO) and clear definition of duties and responsibilities in terms of food organizational structure.

Another likely implication of this theory is that the manager should try to understand the importance the employee attaches to different outcomes and be able to make it known to the subordinates how the outcome could be achieved.

The manager should also be able to analyse the possible results, which different forms of behaviour could bring. In essence, a formalized procedure for rewarding employees in an organization should be established.

Rensis Likert's Approach to Motivation:

The system of management adopted by managers in an organisation depends on the attitude and behaviour of subordinates at work. It is important to note that effective management style and behaviour in one situation is not necessarily effective in a different situation.

In the exploitative-authorities management, managers are highly autocrat and they command and expect compliance. He concentrates on task efficiency and show little regard for the development and morale of subordinates. On the other end of continuum of management, systems, there exists the participative management. In leadership, participation is intended to inspire high productivity and maintain a satisfied workforce. By making subordinates contribute to the decisions that affect them, they feel motivated and respond by making their maximum contribution to the organisation.

If subordinates are lazy, the manager should try to adopt the exploitative authoritative management, but if subordinates should adopt any of the other styles.

2.4 OTHER RELATED LITERATURE

William Ouchi's Theory Z:

Ouchi's theory Z makes a suggestion for culture transformation within the organisation and shows how that can be done. Theory Z type of management is organic, adaptive, cooperative, and productive.

Ouchi came to the conclusion that workers are complete and total human beings and not half machine and half human.

He believed that organisation should put people first and that a working environment, which takes care of the workers, is the sure way to success.

Ouchi, made the following recommendations for *organization*, which want to reach theory Z:

- i. There should be the development of interpersonal skills with emphasis on team work and team spirit.
- ii. Unions must be actively involved in the organization.
- iii. Managers and individuals must appraise themselves.

Characteristics of the Theory Z Model of Management include:

- i. Long term employment
- ii. Collective decision-making
- iii. Individual responsibility
- iv. Implicit, informal evaluation
- v. Holistic concern for people.
- vi. Non-specialized career paths
- vii. Infrequent evaluation and promotion

The managerial implication of Ouchi's theory Z is that theory Z is a fervent plea for genuine human resources development. Managers should endeavour to develop their human resources (employees) because employees are vital for the accomplishment of the goals and objectives of such organization. Ouchi emphasized that through participative management, development of interpersonal skills, long-term employment and so on, workers would be properly motivated and this would result in a better performance by these employees.

2.5 EMPLOYEES PERFORMANCE

The concept of productivity/performance is very important in the organisation, because of its various consequences. People are different and so it is necessary to understand how individual differences may influence work performance (productivity) and job satisfaction. The individual's performance is dependent on three (3) main factors these are:

- The personal attributes of individuals
- The work effort they put forth
- The organization support which they receive

Sources: (Gradarnosi, G. 1996).

The above relationship is expressed in a performance equation as:

Performance = individual attributes X work effort X organisation support.

If any of the three factors is low, the performance/productivity will be low.

- i. **Individual Attribute (personality theory):** These attributes affect employees' productivity/performance in different ways and their importance depends on the nature of a job its task requirement. Three broad categories of individual attributes are of particular relevance to understanding employees' performance. These are demographical characteristics, (age, sex, etc) competency characteristics (aptitude, ability) and psychological characteristics such as extroversion and introversion orientation. Therefore an understanding of individual attributes is vital in doubt a good job.
- ii. **Work Effort (Motivation):** The work effort of an individual otherwise called motivation is one of the determinants of works performance. Motivation described the forces within an individual that account for the level direction and persistence of effort expended at work. However, motivation does not guarantee high level of performance, it has to be combined with individual attributes and organization support to enhance quality and quantity of productivity, Vroom (1964). Although managers should have adequate understanding of motivation so that they can do good jobs of allocating work related rewards.

- iii. **Organization Support:** This is the third components of the individual performance equation. A person who is well fitted to a job and who is highly motivated may not be a good performer, unless there is adequate organization support. Some obstacles to doing a good job are; lack of time, inadequate equipment unclear instructions etc. Therefore, managers require an understanding of organization support so that they can do a good job of planning, organizing, directing and controlling work flow and the work setting etc. the various dimensions of organisation support include group dynamics, organisation size, organisation structure, leadership etc.

In conclusion, managers must understand the needs, goals and abilities of their subordinates and incorporate them into work design. Employees will be more likely to respond by providing individual service in support of organizational performance.

2.6 MEASUREMENT OF PERFORMANCE

There are many appraisal techniques that are used in which organisation must choose. But the chosen of technique is based on their own peculiarity and circumstances, Macarav, D (1970). These techniques include:-

1. **Ranking Methods (comparative standard):** This is the formal systematic method requiring the manager or the superior to rank his subordinates in order of merits usually on their total ability on the job in accordance to a few characteristics. In other words, ranking methods involves the comparison of one person with all other for the purpose of placing them in the rank order of worth.
2. **Grading Techniques or system (Absolute Standard):** In this approach, some categories of worth are established in advance and carefully defined. Employee performance is then compared with this grade and the person is allocated to the grade that best described his/her performance.
3. **Graphic Scales:** Here scales are established in a number of specific factors. Examples of such factors could be in two broad performance:
 - a. Characteristics of the employees
 - b. Contribution of the employees

Characteristics of the employee include loyalty, dependability, personality, leadership etc while contribution of the employees is measured by quantity and quality of work.

4. **Forced – Choice Description:** - This attempt to remove bias or preference accompanying with appraisal techniques by forcing the appraiser or the rates to make a choice with descriptive statements of equal worth.
5. **Management by Objective (MBO):** MBO is a system, which attempts to improve the performance of the company and motivates and trains its employees by integrating their personal goal between the objectives of the company. The use of MBO is an appraisal techniques involve a comparison of actual level of goal attainment against the agreed goals. Decisions are also reached on new goal and possible new strategies that will be of help in the new goal attainment. In using MBO, goals must be clearly established; also the expected performance must be established based on the past performance.

2.7 PROFILE OF OLAM NIGERIA LIMITED

Olam International was founded in the year 1989 and has its headquarters in Singapore. It was established in Nigeria in the year 1995, and headquartered in Lagos State with its branch in Makurdi, Benue State.

The company trades Agricultural Commodities such as, Cocoa, Coffee, Cashew, Sesame, Rice, and Tea.

Its salient features are as follows:

- World's Largest Supplier of cashew, robusta, coffee and sesame.
- Amongst the top three (3) suppliers in cocoa, rice and spices
- Amongst the top three (3) suppliers in peanuts cotton and tropical hardwoods.

The company has the objective of satisfying their customers in all categories. It has staff strength of over five hundred.

The company has sold more than 15 million metric tons of used rail scraps to their numerous customers around the world, which many of them are happy with their products and services to them. Also the hospitality offer to them during the period of time they stay when they come for inspection of the product.

The Organizational Structure of Olam Nigeria Limited

At the Apex of the Company's Organizational Structure are members of the board of directors comprising the General Manager, the manager and also the Controller of Operations (foremen).

The company's General Manager is charged with the responsibility of controlling the day to day running of the industry while the managers and controller of operations are in-charge of the various departments under them.

The Organogram of Olam Nigeria Limited (Organizational Chart):

The General Manager sees to the general administration of the company. He has four assistant managers, these are:- Production Manager, Stores Manager, Sales Manager, and Financial Manager (Accountant)

The Production Manager is in-charge of the day-to-day operations of the company. Directly under him are the workers manager and production supervisor/foreman. Each of these officers supervises the employees in their sections.

The Assistant Personnel Manager is charged with the responsibility of staffing, recruitment, promotion and placement of staff within the company.

The Sales Manager is responsible for sales promotion, advertisement, Research and Development (R & D) Channel of distribution of the company goods etc. directly under him are assistant sales manager west, assistant sales manager north, and assistant sales manager southeast.

The Financial Manager (Accountant) is in-charge of the day-to-day financial recordings and payments of the company's finances and its ramification. He has the assistant accountant and auditor directly reporting to him about the financial transaction of the company.

GENERAL MANAGER

THE OLAM VALUE CHAIN

Integrated across the value chain from farm gate to factory gate

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 INTRODUCTION

The importance of this chapter is to explain the methods of gathering data on the empirical study of the quality and quantity of productivity level enhanced by motivational factors.

The solutions to the problem of staff motivation in order to achieve greater accuracy, efficiency, and effective job productivity in Olam Nigeria Limited are the core of this research work. The approaches thought best are through personal interviews and also the use of questioners. Secondary data, inform of employees salary, past payroll, were used to support the interview and questionnaires so administered.

In the process of identifying and finding, satisfactory explanation to the organizations motivational problems, information were gathered both within the organisation as well as without.

3.2 RESEARCH DESIGN

The design adopted for this study is survey.

3.3 POPULATION OF THE STUDY

Olam Nigeria Limited has its permanent site at Lagos State. The company has four basic production sections which are:

- (i) The processing section which is capital intensive
- (ii) The logistics: Sourcing its products globally
- (iii) Marketing section
- (iv) Distribution section

The company has an objective of satisfying their customers in all categories. The company has staff strength of over five hundred.

3.4 SAMPLE SIZE OF THE STUDY

A total number of one hundred staffers were given a questionnaire to answer. The mode of distribution covers all the production sections in the organisation. The workers, to whom the questionnaires were distributed, were chosen randomly from the study group.

3.5 DATA COLLECTION INSTRUMENTS

Two principal instruments were used in collecting data for this study. These are:

1. Questionnaire
2. Personal interview

Questionnaires

Data were collected by means of questioners, which were administered on the spiel size. The distributions of the questioners were done personally with a brief explanation to the workers concerned.

Personal Interview

This was scheduled for Management Staff and literate junior staff in order to collect relevant data on the structure of authority within the section and department and other useful information under study. The policy on motivation, salary structure of the workers, policy on training and development provided by management. Most of the questions that were asked during the interview were drawn from the questionnaires.

3.6 PROCEDURE FOR PROCESSING AND ANALYZING COLLECTED DATA:

The data collected were analysed by using simple percentages. The personal information data were explained through verbal expression and also, tables were used in analysing the remaining questions.

The hypotheses stated earlier on in this study were tested in order to determine or verify empirically whether thereis any significant differences between the observed and the expected theoretical frequencies obtained from then distribution. In this regards, chi-square

(X2) was used to determine the relationship or the correlation of the various attributes in the tested data.

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1 POPULATION OF THE STUDY SAMPLE

The sample size is one hundred employees of Olam Nigeria Limited, which comprised mainly of junior staffers, which were randomly selected from the four-production section for the convenience of the researcher's work. The stratified sampling technique was employed in this research work. The strata were age, groups, sex, education, skill and length of service.

One hundred questionnaires were evenly distributed among the sections, out of which eighty questionnaires were filled and returned.

Table shows the number of questioners distributed and number returned based on each section.

Table 1: Study Sample Distribution

SECTION	NO. OF DISTRIBUTION	NO. RETURNED
Processing	30	25
Distribution	30	23
Marketing	40	32
TOTAL	100	80

Table I above shows that out of 100 questionnaires distributed to the employees, 90 of them were completed and returned which represent 80% response rate from the respondents. This is considered to be quite a good response for the study samples.

Table II: Age Distribution of Respondents

AGE LEVEL	NO. OF DISTRIBUTION	PERCENTAGE OF RESPONSE
16-35	28	35
36-45	32	40
40-Above	20	25
TOTAL	80	100

Table II above shows that out of 80 questioners returned, 28 are from age bracket of 16-35 representing 35% of response, 32 are aged between 36 – 45 years representing 40%

of the response while 20 were received from the age bracket of 46 and above which represent 25% of the response.

Table III: Income Distribution

MONTHLY INCOME LEVEL	NO. OF DISTRIBUTION	PERCENTATE OF RESPONSE
N10000 – above	20	25
N8000 – 10000	15	18.25
N7000 – N8000	45	56.25
TOTAL	80	100

The table above reveals that 45 respondents fall within the low income level representing 56.25% of the response and their monthly income falls within N7,000 and N8,000: 15 respondents fall within the high income level making up 35% of the response with their monthly income above N10,000. The low-income group constitutes majority of the sample size being studied.

Table IV: Educational Qualification

LEVEL OF EDUCATION	NO. OF DISTRIBUTION	PERCENTAGE OF RESPONSE
B.SC/HND- PH.D	45	56.25
GCE-OND	25	37.5
FSLC	10	6.25
TOTAL	80	100

From the above table, it can be observed that 45 respondents out of the total fall within the high level educational qualification bracket i.e. BSC/HND – PH.D, which respondents 56.25% of the response; 25 of the respondents fall within the medium level i.e. GCE-OND representing a total of 37.5% while 10 respondents fall within the low level i.e. FSCL which represent a total of 6.25% of the response. Those with high level of educational qualification are very more; they include the senior accountants, personnel and finance assistants. Those with medium level of education are mainly GCE ordinary level holders while those with low level education comprise of employees whose educational attainment do not exceed primary or elementary stage. They include messengers and cleaners. They form the unskilled and sometimes semi-skilled labour.

Table V: Length of Services

Length of service here refer to the number of years in employee continues to remain in employment of the company. Table V above shows that our of 80 respondents, 28

11-12 years of service representing 35% of the response, 35 have 6-10 years of service representing 43.75% and 17 have below 5 years of service which represents 21.25% of (lie responses. It shows that 5% of the respondents have worked in the company between 11 and 12 years, 43.73% have been in service between 6 and U) years while 21.25% have worked in the company for 5 years and below.

Table VI: Motivational Impact of Incentives and Salaries

CATEGORY OF STAFF	NO. OF DISTRIBUTION	PERCENTAGE OF RESPONSE
Yes	60	75
No	20	25
TOTAL	80	100

The above table indicates that there are 60 respondents from the “yes” category of staff representing 75% of the responses, 20 respondents from the “No” category representing 25% of the total response out of the 80 questionnaires returned 75% of the staff strongly agreed that they would derive much satisfaction from incentives/salaries if given to them. While 25% of the “No” category disagreed that they derive a substantial level of satisfaction from incentives/salaries.

The above analysis shows that given incentive/salaries to the employees in the company appear to be a more appropriate means of motivating staff.

Table VII: Impact of Motivation on Employees’ Relation will, Management

CATEGORY OF STAFF	NO. OF DISTRIBUTION	PERCENTAGE OF RESPONSE
Excellent	18	22.5
Good	23	28.75
Fair	39	48.75
TOTAL	80	100

Table VII shows that out of the 80 respondents there are 18 respondents in the excellent category which represents 22.5% of the total responses, 23 respondents are from the “good” category representing 28.75% of the responses, while 39 respondents are from the fair category which represent 48.75% of the total responses.

Viewing the above table, the respondents in all categories believed that when they are adequately motivated by management, either through training in related discipline or through incentive, they would put in more efforts for the betterment of the company, be more punctual to work at all time and even make sacrifices in terms of working during weekends and or public holidays without asking to be compensated by way of overtime payments. From

the above analysis, it would seem that motivation of the employees in the company allow for workers punctuality to work and increase efforts towards improving their level of productivity.

Table VIII: Impact of Motivation on Employees Attitude to Work

IMPACT ON ATTITUDE	NO. OF DISTRIBUTION	PERCENTAGE OF RESPONSE
Positively	70	87.5
Negatively	10	12.5
TOTAL	80	100

From the above table, there are 70 respondents from the positive category of staff which represents 87.5%, 10 respondents from the negative category of staff which represents 12.5% of the total responses. Looking at the responses, 87.5% of the total respondents strongly agreed with the view that motivational factors help to reduce absenteeism to the barest minimum, while 12.5% disagreed with this view.

From the above analysis, it would appear that when staff are motivated they will be regular to work reduce absenteeism and be more dedicated to their jobs.

4.2 PRESENTATION OF DATA ACCORDING TO TEST OF HYPOTHESIS

The following hypothesis were tested in this research in order to determine or verify empirically whether there is any significant difference between the observed and the expected theoretical frequencies obtained from the distribution. In this regards, the chi-square (X^2) was used for the correlation of the various attributes in the tested data.

Hypothesis 1:

H₀: An increase in the salary/fringe benefits in an organisation does not lead to an increase in the productivity of workers.

H₁: The greater the salary/fringe benefits in an organisation, the greater the productivity of workers.

To test the above hypothesis, the table below which shows the responses of both (A) and (A) respectively was used. The letter “A” represents the views of all respondents who agreed that salary/fringe benefits should be increased in order to lead to an increase in worker’s productivity, while the letter “A” represents the views of all the respondents who disagreed with the above claim.

The Decision Rule is as Follows:

- a) Accept the null hypothesis if the calculated X^2 value is greater than the table value X^2 . The rejection of the null hypothesis leads to the acceptance of the alternative hypothesis and vice versa.

Three hypotheses would be tested and interpreted separately using the formula $\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O - E)^2}{E}$ (0-)

Where: O = Observed Frequency
 E = Expected Frequency
 \sum = Summation
 χ^2 = The value of Chi-square

Data Collected

Response:	Fo	Fe
Agreed (A)	59	40
Disagreed (A ¹)	21	40
TOTAL	80	100

Where $F_o = 59 + 21 = 80$
 $F_e = 100 - 2 = 40$

Contingency Table:

Fo	Fe	Fo-Fe	(Fo-Fe) ²	(Fo-Fe) ²	3(Fo-Fe) ²
59	40	19	361	Fe	Fe
				3.025	3.025
21	40	19	361	3.025	3.025

Calculated $\chi^2 = 6.05$

Tabulated $\chi^2 = 3.846$

From one contingency table, the calculated χ^2 is greater than the tabulated χ^2 . Thus, the alternative hypothesis (H_1) which states that the greater the salary/fringe benefits in an organisation the greater the productivity of workers should be accepted while the null hypothesis (H_0) should be rejected.

Hypothesis 2:

Data Collected:

Response:	Fo	Fe
Agree (A)	69	40
Disagreed (A ¹)	11	40
TOTAL	80	100

Contingency Table:

Fo	Fe	Fo-Fe	(F0-Fe) ²	(Fo-Fe) ²	3(Fo-Fe) ²
69	40	29	841	<u>Fe</u>	<u>Fe</u>
				21.025	21.025
21	40	-19	361	21.025	<u>21.025</u>
					<u>42.05</u>

Calculated X² = 42.05

Tabulated X² – 3.8414

From the contingency table, since the tabulated X² = 3.841 is less than the calculated X² = 42.05, we will reject H₀ and accept alternative hypothesis (H₁) which states that employees will perform better if they are promised some sort of rewards.

Hypothesis 3:

Response:	Fo	Fe
Agreed (A)	70	40
Disagreed (A ¹)	10	40
TOTAL	80	80

Where Fo: = 70 + 10 = 80

Fe = 80 – 2 = 40

Contingency Table:

Fo	Fe	Fo-Fe	$(Fo-Fe)^2$	$(Fo-Fe)^2$	$3(Fo-Fe)^2$
70	40	30	900	<u>Fe</u>	<u>Fe</u>
				22.5	22.5
10	40	-30	900	22.5	22.5
					<u>45</u>

Calculated X2 = 45

Tabulated X2 = 3.841

The tabulated value X2 = 3.841 is less than the calculated value X2 45. Therefore, the decision would be to reject H0 and accept iii, which asserts that the best performance is a function of motivational factors.

4.3 FINDINGS

Based on the interviews conducted by the researchers, the questionnaire analysis and he test o hypothesis carried out, the following were identified.

- (i) Motivation does not guarantee high level of performance; it has to be combined with individual attributes and organization support to enhance productivity and performance.
- (ii) Effective performance would seem to require the motivation, the ability and traits, and the clear understanding of the job demands.
- (iii) It was also reviewed that some employees may be happy, but remains unproductive.

5.0 SUMMARY, RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSION

5.1 Summary

The aim of this study is to determine how the staff in Olam Nigeria Limited could be motivated through rewards in order to improve the quality and quantity of their productivity.

Many theories have been propounded by various authors about factors used by managers to motivate employees among which are promotion, challenging assignments, job recognition, relation with workers and supervisors, technical supervision, increased responsibilities, job security, growth in the organisation, employee benefits, the work itself, work groups, management policies and the use of rewards as a standard of appraising the employees work.

5.2 Conclusion

It must be remembered that the manager cannot, all by himself perform all the tasks his scheduled of responsibilities. As such, he must find ways of making his subordinates want to work with him and for him, it is however, important to note that human beings respond favourable to stimuli, amongst which human dignity is one of the most important. It therefore, means that if dignity is violated, conflict will arise within individual employees and

as well as between the individual and group. As a result, the individual can become less productive than he or she would otherwise have been. Such frustrating conflict affects his work output as well as a loss of goodwill towards the company, disruption of group harmony, inability to meet company production schedules thereby resulting in decreased profitability.

5.3. Recommendations

Based on the summary drawn from the study, the following recommendations are hereby proposed:

- i. **Adequate Rewards:** The Management of Olam Nigeria Company should embark on managing by results through the offering of a good package of incentive to the employees in order to manage them to perform even better and hence achieve the goals for which it was incorporated. Such incentives should include productivity bonus, non-absenteeism bonus and utility allowances for all categories of employees whose duties demand extra working hours on a daily basis so as to encourage them to work at all times. However, if these motivational factors are lacking in the company, the tendency might be that the employees would put up a dysfunctional attitude towards their jobs, a situation that might spell “doom” for the company especially in terms of keeping competition for scarce resources both human and material.
- ii. **Good Supervision and Relationship between Employees and their Supervisors:** This should be encouraged in the company. The reason being that when employees can discuss freely with their supervisor about their problems, then supervisors would be able to offer suggestions or solutions to these problems. This would make employees become happy and work tirelessly in order to ensure that they do not go against the rules and regulations, which might offend the superior. Such good relations bring about goodwill and job satisfaction on the part of the employees; which is the aim of every profit making organisation.
- iii. **Conducive Job Environment:** Conducive job environment in this context is viewed as everything that surrounds the individual worker such as available space, heating, lighting ventilation, job security, standard of hygiene and safety. The attractiveness of a work environment has an impact on the motivation of a group of employees. Management should try as much as possible to make the work environment very conducive for its employees, in terms of job security, the company should avoid retrenching, forcing resignation of appointment or laying off its workforce because when employees are assured of the continuity of their jobs, in these times of the economic recession, they would be fully productive in order to sustain the growth of the company which will in turn guarantee the continued retention of these jobs.
- iv. **Free-flow of Information:** Management must ensure that individual employees know what his or her job entails and how such fits in with the overall work scheme of the organization. In this way, the employees would feel that their usefulness in the organization and the recognition of their abilities rest on how well and dedicated they perform their tasks. Employees would be well motivated as long as they are aware of the standards expected of them, and how to use any equipment in their work environment, which is relevant to their duties or
- v. **Dealing Groups:** To win the confidence of the group, the manager should not regard himself as a supervisor being, but as a member of the team, which has joint

responsibilities. This is very useful for motivating employees because individual members of a group adhere to their common norms, which also sustain high standard of work when favourable conditions are provided. Therefore to perceive the manager as a member of the group facilitates the commitment of subordinates to the objectives or goals set by the manager as well as those set by the organization. In general, the manager must realize that his effectiveness will depend largely on his treatment of his subordinates. He should respect his subordinates by creating the kind of atmosphere in which the subordinates can give their honest best.

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APPENDIX A

Department of Business Administration,
Benue State Polytechnic,
Ugbokolo, Benue State.

Date: 22nd December, 2009.

Dear Sir/Madam,

QUESTIONNAIRE

The researcher is an undergraduate student in the above named Polytechnic and is undertaking an academic study of this organization - Olam Nigeria Limited. The questions contained in this questionnaire are designed to seek your views and feelings about motivational factors and its impact on the productivity of workers in the company. This is purely an academic exercise and as such, any information supplied shall be treated with strict confidentiality.

You are therefore requested to please complete this questionnaire as accurately as possible.

Yours sincerely,

NKECHI OFFIA

QUESTIONNARE

SECTION A (PERSONAL DATA)

Please tick in the appropriate box or write out relevant information, to indicate your response.

1. Sex: Male[] Female []
2. Age: (a) 16-25[] (b) 26-35 [] (c) 36-45 [] (d) 46-above
3. Educational Qualifications:
 (a) FSLC []
 (b) GCE-OND []
 (c) HND-PH.D []
4. Marital Status:
 (a) Single[] (b) Married [] (c) Divorced [] (d) Widow []
5. Monthly Income:
 N1,500 – N3,500 []
 N3,501 – N4,500 []
 N6,001 and above []
6. How long have you been in the company?
 Below 5 years []
 6- 10 years []
 11- 22 years []

SECTION B: (SELECTED QUESTIONS)

7. Is there any relationship between your salary and the satisfaction you derive from your work?
Yes No
8. Assuming your salary is decreased, how will it affect your level of productivity?
9. What do you perceive as a source of job satisfaction?
Higher Pay Conducive job environment
10. Are you satisfied with your job?
Yes No
11. If no, why are not satisfied? _____
-
12. Which of the following motivates you most in the organization?
- a. Salary/Fringe benefits
 - b. Conducive working environment
 - c. Cordial relationship with your manager and subordinates
13. Would you consider these factors as adequate?
Yes No
14. Has this increased your productivity? Yes No
15. Do you consider work your working environment conducive?
Yes No
16. How has it affected your productivity?
Higher Lower Average
17. If your level of expectation on the environment is not met, would your productivity remain the same?
Yes No
18. How cordial is your relationship with your manager and your subordinates? Excellent Good Fair
19. How has it affected your productivity? Positively Negatively
20. In your candid opinion, what do you feel about uncaring bosses/subordinates?
- a. Dampen morale/productivity
 - b. High labour turnover
 - c. Indifferent
21. Does your Boss appreciate when a good job is done?
Yes No
22. If yes, has it increased your productivity? Yes No
23. What motivates you least?
- a. Salary/fringe benefits
 - b. Working environment
 - c. Relationship with subordinates
 - d. Canteen services
 - e. Medical facilities
24. Does it have effect on your productivity? Yes No